

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND FAILURE
MAPS FOR SHORT FIBRE/POLYMER MATRIX
COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Fracture toughness values (K_Q) of short glass and carbon fibre reinforced injection-moulded semicrystalline poly (phenylene-sulfide) (PPS), poly (ether-ether-ketone) (PEEK) and polyamide 6.6 (PA 6.6) were determined at different crosshead speeds ($v = 10^{-1} \dots 10^3$ mm/min) and in a broad temperature range ($T = -60 \dots 200^\circ\text{C}$). The results were summarized in form of fracture maps, having the fracture toughness (K_Q) and the elastic modulus (E) as the axes. Failure was characterized by the use of scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The results were reported in failure maps, spanning the field of testing temperatures and strain rates used. They show fields of dominance of certain failure mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

The widespread high-temperature engineering application of short fibre-reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites (SFRP) necessitates to characterize the time and temperature dependence of their mechanical properties. For the user of these materials it is of importance to have clear informations about changes in properties such as fracture toughness and stiffness with environmental temperature and loading rate. The interest of the SFRP manufacturers is focussed on the microscopic failure behaviour, since only its knowledge can lead to further improvement of their materials. One way to illustrate the results in a compact form, is the construction of property maps. In earlier papers, this kind of maps were used to show the interrelation of macroscopic properties (e.g. fracture energy) with fibre related parameters and failure events [1]. Quite recently, macroscopic properties were plotted separately from those events which occurred on microscopic level, thus E-modulus maps ($E = f(\text{temperature, frequency})$) [2] and fracture energy and failure maps [3] appeared in the literature. Instead of the fracture energy (G_C), the fracture toughness (K_Q) can also be used for mapping, but it must be kept in mind that K_Q is a function of both, fracture energy (G_C) and elastic modulus (E), via $K_Q = \sqrt{G_C \cdot E}$.

In the present paper, fracture toughness and elastic modulus as a function of testing temperature and deformation rate were used to establish fracture maps for different short fibre-reinforced engineering polymers (PPS = polyphenylenesulfide, PEEK = polyetheretherketone, PA 6.6 = polyamide 6.6). In addition, their typical breakdown mechanisms were summarized in form of failure maps.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Both, PPS and its short fibre composites (30 % glass (GF) and 30 % carbon (CF)) as well as PEEK and its GF- and CF-reinforced composites (20 and 30 % GF and 30 % CF)) were available as injection-moulded rectangular plates of about 6 and 3 mm thickness, respectively. PPS systems were based on Ryton PPS (Philips Petroleum Co., USA) while those of PEEK were standard Victrex PEEK grades (ICI Ltd, UK). PA 6.6 and both its 30

and 50 % chopped short (SGF) and long GF (LGF) reinforced composites were supplied as edge gated discs injection moulded from marketed Maranyl and Verton PA 6.6 grades (ICI Ltd., UK).

CT specimens, $36 \times 35 \text{ mm}^2$ in size were cut from the mouldings, with notches either perpendicular or parallel to the melt flow direction (MFD) (designated as T- and L-cracked specimens, respectively). The initial notches were sharpened with a razor blade prior to the static loading experiments. The latter were carried out on a Zwick 1445 testing machine at different crosshead speeds ($v = 10^{-1} \dots 10^3 \text{ mm/min}$) and temperatures ($T = -60 \dots 200^\circ\text{C}$).

The calculation of the fracture toughness (K_Q or K_C) was performed according to ASTM E 399 standards. From the load-displacement curves of the CT specimens the initial slope was read (E_{in}) and either treated as an indirect measure for the E-modulus, or by its use a E-modulus calculation could be performed according to the elastic compliance expression of Saxena and Hudak [4] .

More detailed informations on the machining of the samples, the fracture toughness measurements, and the microscopic characterization of the materials' microstructures and their failure performances are available from previous papers [5-9] .

RESULTS

Figure 1 reports the fracture toughness vs E-modulus functions for the GF- (Fig. 1a) and CF-reinforced PPS (Fig. 1b), respectively. In these maps solid lines represent isodeformation-rate contours, while dashed ones are isothermal contours. For both type of composites, the map region lying, for example, above the normalized value $K_C^{**} = 0.8$ indicates all testing conditions for which K_C of the material is at least 80 % that of the arbitrary chosen standard (at $T = \text{RT}$, $v = 10^1 \text{ mm/min}$). The region to the right of $E^{**} = 0.8$ represents again all conditions for which the modulus is at least 80 % of the standard. If engineering use of these SFRP requires that both E^{**} and K_C^{**} lie above 80 % then materials are restricted to both low deformation rates ($v \leq 10^1 \text{ mm/min}$) and a temperature range up

to about 90°C ($T = 90^\circ\text{C} \approx T_g$).

Fig. 1. Fracture maps (normalized K_C^{**} vs. normalized E^{**} , at different temperatures and crosshead speeds) for:

- 30 % GF-PPS. The values of the standard (30 % GF-PPS at room temperature (RT) and $v = 10^1$ mm/min) are: $K_C = 4 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ and $E_{in} = 9.2 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N/m}$.
- 30 % CF-PPS, dto. with $K_C = 3.8 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ and $E_{in} = 1.1 \cdot 10^6 \text{ N/m}$.

SEM-analysis of crack paths on polished sides of CT-samples as well as their fracture surfaces leads to the conclusion that 3 major failure mechanisms dominate the actual fracture process:

- ductile matrix yielding or brittle matrix fracture
- pull-out of fibers aligned mostly perpendicular to the crack front
- fibre/matrix separation in case of fibres parallel oriented in the crack plane.

The T vs v area of the failure map in Fig. 2 may be divided into 3 sections (A, B and C). In region "A" the failure of the impact-toughened PPS matrix of the GF-PPS occurs ductilely. Since fibre pull-out is restricted on a short fibre length (mostly for the fibre ends) the main energy absorbing process should be a plastic deformation of the matrix. Reducing $T < T_g$ ("B" region) matrix embrittlement takes place. The plane of this brittle fracture is almost identical with that of the notch. In such a way fibre pull-out extends over a longer fibre distance. In the "C" region, stress concentration at the fibre ends may induce multiple brittle matrix cracking. The 3 principle breakdown mechanisms mentioned above are illustrated schematically in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Failure map for the GF-reinforced PPS composite

Figure 3. Failure modes schematically, proposed for short fibre reinforced PPS composites

In a similar way as reported for PPS, the results obtained with PEEK and its short fibre composites can be plotted. The fracture maps shown in Fig. 4 for GF-PEEK (Fig. 4a) and CF-PEEK (Fig. 4b), respectively, do not indicate any significant change in K_Q for these two types of composites.

The only difference concerns the E-modulus due to the great difference in moduli of the GF and CF.

Figure 4. Fracture maps (K_Q vs E curves for the PEEK composites of an average reinforcing effectiveness ($R = 0.1$), at different temperatures and crosshead speeds) for:
 a) GF-reinforced; b) CF-reinforced PEEK composites

Figure 5 represents the failure maps of the PEEK matrix and its short fibre-reinforced composites established by fractography.

Figure 5. Failure maps for the PEEK matrix (a) and for its short fibre-reinforced composites (b).

The failure maps are analogous to each other since three different breakdown processes could be distinguished. At $T < 90^\circ\text{C}$ and $v < 10^2$ mm/min the matrix deforms ductilely (A region) while the fibres break - eventually with some pull-out of the fibre end - resulting in high K_Q -values. At $v \geq 10^2$ mm/min brittle matrix fracture was observed with fibre pull-out yielding very low K_Q values. Intermediate K_Q values were measured at $T > 90^\circ\text{C}$ where viscous matrix yielding occurs with fibre/matrix separation.

Figs. 6 and 7 report K_Q values in function of temperature (T) and fibre volume fraction (V_f) for SGF- and LGF-reinforced PA 6.6 composites at $v = 10^0$ (Fig. 5) and 10^3 mm/min (Fig. 6) crosshead speed, respectively. Shaded areas indicate additional effects caused by the LGF of very high

aspect ratio.

Figure 6. K_Q vs (T, V_F) functions for SGF- and LGF-reinforced PA 6.6 composites at $v = 10^0$ mm/min crosshead speed

Figure 7. K_Q vs (T, V_F) functions for SGF- and LGF-reinforced PA 6.6 composites at $v = 10^3$ mm/min crosshead speed

The failure map of the PA 6.6 composites contains again three different regions characterizing the main failure processes. Below ambient temperature the matrix breakdown is brittle, and all types of fibre related

processes (fracture, debonding, pull-out) could be found. Between RT and T_g , the matrix fractures in a mixed manner (brittle and microductile due to crazing) and fibre pull-out and debonding predominate. Above T_g , viscous matrix flow with fibre/matrix separation was observed. Increasing the crosshead speed causes a shift of the boarder lines between the above regions to higher temperatures.

In general it can be stated, that these maps help to predict the way in which the materials fail, and they may give guidance in applying toughening methods. Also, the ideal experimental conditions for studying a particular failure mechanism can be read directly from this type of map [10] .

CONCLUSIONS

Fracture toughness maps (K_{Ic} vs. E as a function of T and v) as well as failure maps were generated for different short fiber filled engineering polymers (PPS, PEEK, PA 6.6). The first group can serve as valuable tools for material users in selecting materials for special purposes. The second type of illustration helps to understand the failure behavior of these materials in a more systematic way, thus allowing the materials manufacturer in following steps to tailor-make the material's behavior in directions desired.

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